

FEATURES OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING OF THE KIDNEYS IN CHILDREN IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF ACUTE AND CHRONIC GLOMERULONEPHRITIS

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Abstract. *It is important to suggest that recent advances in functional and quantitative renal magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) studies have enabled the development of methods capable of generating quantitative imaging biomarkers. These biomarkers may significantly improve the treatment of kidney diseases. In particular, MRI methods have significant potential for detecting early signs of renal damage, for in-depth understanding of the pathogenesis of underlying diseases, for individual prognostic stratification of patients, and for monitoring their response to therapy. MRI biomarkers are unique among diagnostic tools because they provide high spatial detail of the entire kidney, allow detection of corticomedullary changes and differences between the left and right kidneys, and assess the degree of functional heterogeneity within the kidney. Serial MRI studies can reveal structural and functional changes, providing valuable information on the progression of kidney disease.*

Keywords: *renal structures, MRI examination, chronic glomerulonephritis, renal magnetic resonance imaging, edema, inflammation, fibrosis and vascularization changes.*

Objective. To study the features of renal magnetic resonance imaging in children in the diagnosis of acute and chronic glomerulonephritis.

Material and methods of the study. In our studies, 35 (21.9%) children with glomerulonephritis underwent MRI, including 18 (51.4%) children with acute glomerulonephritis (GN) and 17 (48.6%) children with chronic course.

Definitely, MRI of the kidneys in children required a special approach related to age and health status. A detailed description was provided to patients or their parents, and the consent form was signed before the MRI examination. In older children, magnetic resonance imaging was performed during the sleep phase, and no drugs were administered either before or during the study. In our studies, appropriate sedation methods or general anesthesia with high diagnostic efficiency were used for younger children. While interpreting the MRI results, age-related features of the renal structures in children were taken into account. To visualize the kidneys in children, we used a special MRI scanning mode using high-resolution sequences, which provided the best visualization. MRI was performed on a 3.0 T superconducting magnet (Signa Architect (GE), USA) with a surface coil.

Study results. MRI allowed us to evaluate in detail the morphological and functional changes in the kidneys in children with glomerulonephritis. The use of various sequences and contrast enhancement made it possible to identify edema, inflammation, fibrosis and vascularization changes, which was important for diagnosis and treatment planning.

Besides that, all patients had continuous multispiral images in the coronal projection (slice thickness 3.5-3.8 mm) using the T1WI technique - to assess the anatomy of the kidneys and corticomedullary differentiation. T2WI - to detect edema and inflammatory changes in the

kidneys, T2-weighted images with fat suppression were also used for better visualization of edema and inflammation, and diffusion-weighted images (DWI) - to assess diffuse changes in kidney tissue that indicated inflammation or fibrosis, the scanning time was 4 minutes 40 seconds. The imaging parameters included a data acquisition matrix of 280 X 212 pixels and a field of view of 360 x 240 mm.

During the research there was studied the MRI semiotics of kidney lesions in children with acute and chronic glomerulonephritis. Table 1 presents the features of differential diagnostic MRI semiotics of kidney lesions to identify acute and chronic glomerulonephritis in children.

Table 1.

Differential diagnostic MRI semiotics of kidney lesions in acute and chronic glomerulonephritis

Parameters	Acute Glomerulonephritis	Chronic glomerulonephritis
Kidney size	Increased size due to inflammation and edema	Decreased size due to progressive fibrosis
Cortico-medullary differentiation	Decreased size due to edema and inflammation	Decreased or no differentiation due to fibrotic changes
T1WI signal characteristics	Minor changes, possible signal decrease with significant edema	Decreased signal due to replacement of normal tissue by fibrous tissue
T2WI signal characteristics	Increased signal indicating edema	Mixed signal reflecting fibrosis and possible areas of inflammation
Fat-suppressed T2-weighted images	Increased signal indicating edema	Mixed signal reflecting fibrosis and chronic inflammation
Diffusion-weighted images (DWI)	Limited water diffusion in inflamed tissue, decreased diffusion coefficient (ADC)	Restriction of water diffusion in fibrous tissue, decrease in the diffusion coefficient (ADC)

It should be suggested that in acute glomerulonephritis in children, inflammation was accompanied by an increase in kidney size, edema, and impaired corticomedullary differentiation. Increased signal on T2-weighted images and limited diffusion on DWI. At the same time, MRI images in children with chronic glomerulonephritis revealed characteristic signs of a decrease in kidney size, fibrosis, and loss of corticomedullary differentiation, as well as a mixed signal on T2-weighted images and limited diffusion on DWI. Table 2 presents the MRI semiotics of acute and chronic glomerulonephritis in children.

In the study of children with AGN, 16 (88.9%) patients had an increase in kidney size, an increase in volume was also noted, this sign was characterized by an acute inflammatory process and due to edema, but at the same time, 13 (76.4%) children with CGN had a decrease in the size

and volume of the kidneys, which developed due to progressive fibrosis and sclerosis. In 9 (50.0%) children with AGN and in 4 (23.5%) children with CGN, a complete loss of corticomedullary differentiation was noted on T2WI images. In patients with T1 nephrotic syndrome, the renal parenchyma was enlarged, without loss of corticomedullary differentiation. Bilateral enlargement of the kidneys was also observed in children with AGN.

Table 2.

MRI semiotics of acute and chronic glomerulonephritis in children

Parameter	Acute glomerulonephritis	Chronic glomerulonephritis
Kidney size (length, mm)	Increase (more than 110 mm)	Decreased (less than 90 mm)
Kidney volume (ml)	Increase (more than 150 ml)	Decreased (less than 120 ml)
Diffusion coefficient (ADC, $\times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$)	Decreased (0.8-1.2)	Decreased (0.6-1.0)
Signal on T2-weighted images (relative signal) (RSI)	Increase (RSI > 1.5)	Mixed (RSI 1.0-1.5)

In T1-weighted images (T1-WI) due to edema, a decrease in the signal in the cortex was noted in all patients with AGN, but in T2-WI, an increase in the signal in the cortex was revealed due to inflammation and edema.

A characteristic feature of AGN was an increase in the signal on DWI, which was characterized by edema and inflammation, which led to a limitation of water diffusion and a decrease in the diffusion coefficient (ADC). In children with CGN, a heterogeneous decrease in the signal in the cortex due to fibrotic changes in T1-WI was noted, and in T2-WI, a heterogeneous decrease in the signal in the cortex and medulla due to fibrosis and scarring was also revealed. Changes indicative of fibrosis and sclerosis were visible, including a decrease in the volume of the renal parenchyma and its replacement with connective tissue. Chronic changes resulted in increased water diffusion, which was manifested by a decrease in the signal in diffusion-weighted MRI (DWI) and, accordingly, an increase in the diffusion coefficient (ADC) was noted. The increase in ADC values is due to increased diffusion in fibrous tissue.

Conclusions. By summarizing it should be suggested that MRI allows detailed visualization and differentiation of acute and chronic changes in glomerulonephritis. In the acute stage, signs of inflammation and edema predominate, while the chronic process is characterized by a decrease in the size of the kidneys, fibrosis and sclerosis. Diffusion-weighted MRI additionally improves the assessment of inflammatory and fibrotic changes.

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